

THE SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL NEED OF FORMING COLLABORATIVE COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS

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Abstract: In this article, the socio-pedagogical necessity of forming collaborative competence in elementary school students is researched and theoretically based.

Key words: collaboration, creativity, cooperation, partnership, integration, education in the field.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kollaborativ kompetentlikni shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik zarurati tadqiq etilgan va nazariy asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: kollaboratsiya, ijodiylik, hamkorlik, sherikchilik, integratsiya, hamorlikdagi ta'lim.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется и теоретически обосновывается социально-педагогическая необходимость формирования совместной компетентности у учащихся младших классов.

Ключевые слова: сотрудничество, творчество, кооперация, партнерство, интеграция, образование в сфере.

At the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, in the course of reforms, the tasks of creative approach to each sector and the renewed structure, carrying out modernization work on the basis of creativity are gaining relevance. Because creativity and creative cooperation are the most important features for a modernized society. For this, it is important to support young people in every way, to provide them with work, to create conditions for them to acquire modern knowledge and skills, to realize their abilities and talents, and to create suitable conditions for these works by the government. That is why it is necessary to develop collaborative skills in students from primary education.

Collaboration refers to the partnership of two or more people to achieve a common good together. Collaboration in primary education refers to the learning and educational process based on the creative cooperation and partnership of students.

Creative collaboration is the joint creative work of two or more creators. Artists who are close to each other in relation to social life, life experience, profession and mathlab, faith, language, aesthetic ideas, creative style or direction can carry out certain scientific and creative activities together. Therefore, creative cooperation of students means joint creative work based on closeness of life experiences, scientific interests, field and creative style.

According to philosophers, creativity is the original essence that belongs to the subject itself and the external world at the same time. Creativity and creativity cannot be realized without the participation of high creativity - subjectivity and is realized only by the characteristic of a creative person[1]. Therefore, the qualities of high creativity are an important feature of creativity.

In pedagogy, creativity mainly means inventiveness, originality, imagination, sensitivity, ability to solve problems quickly. It is emphasized that this ability is versatile[2]. Creativity is the potential ability to think, feel, and act in a comprehensive way. "It is the ability of a person to get out of problematic situations in a unique way through his thinking, to approach it creatively. Creativity can be called a desire for creativity, a creative approach to life, a constant critical look at oneself and analysis. Also, creative thinking means approaching something from different angles. Every person is born with creative abilities. It is up to the teacher to guide and develop it»[3]. In pedagogy, creativity is understood as a person's "creative ability" and is analyzed in relation to the level of intellectual development. In particular, A. Arifjanova explained the essence of the concept of creativity in connection with the development of the creative potential of pedagogues in the following way: "by mobilizing appropriate opportunities, it is interpreted as the ability of a person to accept a problem and create a new, unusual product". According to G. Ibragimova, creativity - it is manifested as a set of skills related to creativity, creative qualities of a person. Creativity includes a high level of sensitivity to problems, intuition, anticipation of results, fantasy, research and reflection»[3].

In our opinion, collaboration is an integrative skill that is full of interrelated skills and elements. For example, creative abilities include: imagination, fantasy, dreaming and the development of unique abilities. Creativity is the main, but not the only, ability that supports heuristic cognitive activity. As a result of creative and instrumental activity, the process of learning is definitely realized in students. In this, creative and cognitive activities are carried out together. Therefore, creative cooperation is also a type of joint creative and cognitive activity of students. Through this, they exchange ideas with each other, conduct scientific activities in cooperation.

In the formation of collaborative skills in elementary school students, they can solve the following tasks:

- arming with theoretical knowledge in mastering collaboration as a socio-cultural value, a set of conscious actions aimed at creating innovation;
- to introduce the axiological, intellectual and functional foundations of collaboration, to give an understanding of the factors of its implementation;
- creating an understanding of the general social and creative nature of the student who creates and implements collaboration, as well as the characteristics of its embodiment in concrete professional activity;
- fostering the ability to promote creative ideas and analyze the process of their implementation;
- to show creativity, to form the skills of their practical implementation;
- creating the ability to perform strategic, tactical, operational tasks related to creative cooperation;
- as well as mastering the values of creative cooperation by students, determining the necessary individual competence in their creative activity, creating a basis for its further strengthening, etc.

By forming collaborative skills in primary school students, it will be possible to develop the following qualities:

- aspiration;
- having creativity;

- superiority of logical thinking ability;
- ability to search;
- propensity for innovation;
- high analytical thinking ability;
- high synthetic thinking ability;
- high level of knowledge;
- strong desire for creative cooperation.

Based on the priority signs of the formation of collaborative skills in elementary school students, the problem of creative cooperation includes many independent issues and defines a number of conceptual rules. These require students to develop concrete technological issues on the basis of creative cooperation.

These include:

- creation of technologies related to pedagogical bases of development of creative cooperation skills;
- formation of a system of ideas about creative cooperation among elementary school students;
- pedagogical tools that ensure the connection of the components of education in the process of creative activity;
- creating an environment of creative cooperation in primary education;
- technological and methodical factors affecting the identification of individual characteristics in the development of creative cooperation skills.

Reforming the field of education, which is a very complex field of activity such as the formation of an all-round mature person, is a very comprehensive activity, taking into account the radical changes implemented in this field, it is necessary to understand how creative activity will bring about positive changes in the education of the creative specialist who conducts it. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to a new interpretation of education in our country, fundamentally different from traditional pedagogy. Characterization of educational work as a process of learning, which is not only carried out by a pedagogue, but also actively carried out by a student who is a participant in this activity, is a unique ideological basis of new pedagogical technologies. According to him, in the process of education and training, the main focus is not on imparting ready-made knowledge to the learner, but on acquiring knowledge through independent reflection, expressing one's own point of view, defending it, and developing the principle of education in the process of pedagogical activity after turning any knowledge into practical skills and competences. implementation is envisaged.

In fact, in order to develop creative abilities, students should have such qualities as promoting an independent opinion, justifying it, defending their own opinions, objecting to insufficiently substantiated opinions, inquisitiveness, initiative, completing the work started, and taking responsibility for the results of creative cooperation activities. can be formed during training.

When setting educational goals aimed at forming collaborative skills in primary school students, it is recommended to take into account the following requirements:

1. The analysis of existing needs and problems serves as the main basis for goal setting, firstly, the initial opportunities, tools, and secondly, the student's personal knowledge reserves;

2. Goals should be relevant enough to solve important problems;
3. Goals should be complex, but realistic;
4. The goals should be clearly formulated (with the exact level of the desired result and the deadline for achieving it) (the easier it will be to determine their achievement).
5. Goals should be diagnostic, motivating, exhorting.
6. Objectives match the student's tasks. to be within the framework of near future development
7. The goals of the cooperative activity should be known to all its participants, understood and accepted by them (this requires unity of collective activities and goals).
8. Smaller specific goals should be subordinated to larger and long-term goals and aspirations.

In conclusion, the development of creative cooperation skills in students remains one of the necessary social requirements of today. Therefore, it is one of the important tasks to carry out research on the creation of an effective pedagogical model and conditions for the development of creative cooperation skills in primary school students, thereby developing a specific result-oriented educational technology.

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